

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Analysis of nocturnal urban heat advection using crowd weather stations

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Abstract

Urban areas are increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, with growing populations exposed to extreme weather. Understanding urban weather dynamics is essential, yet professional weather stations are often located outside cities, limiting their ability to capture urban-specific phenomena. Crowdsourced data from privately owned “Crowd Weather Stations” (CWS) offers a promising alternative, providing dense spatial coverage to study processes like the urban heat island (UHI). While the UHI is commonly examined under ideal calm conditions, such scenarios are rare, and the role of wind in spreading urban heat to downwind areas is often overlooked. This study analyzes nocturnal urban heat advection (UHA) using five years (2019–2023) of crowdsourced weather data from Paris, France, and Berlin, Germany, from several thousand CWS. We first develop a framework to quantify the UHA effect from CWS data, taking into account the strength of the UHI during individual cases with respect to the average conditions. Results show that wind intensifies heat exposure significantly downwind of city cores, with the strongest effects at wind speeds around $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The advection effect decreases gradually with distance from the urban core and varies with wind direction. These findings highlight the importance of accounting for UHA to improve our understanding of urban heat exposure and its spatial variability, particularly in downwind regions. This study provides a framework for utilizing dense crowdsourced data to link conditions in the atmospheric boundary layer better with those in the urban canopy layer.

KEYWORDS

citizen weather stations, crowd weather stations, crowdsourcing, urban heat advection, urban heat island

1 | INTRODUCTION

Detailed knowledge of urban thermal conditions is essential for planners and policymakers to implement adequate heat mitigation and adaptation measures. However, the characterization of intra-urban spatially heterogeneous

urban overheating is challenging due to a lack of dense urban meteorological networks. Professional weather stations, required for a dense observation network, are expensive to set up and maintain over longer periods of time and, if available, mostly situated outside cities (Oke, 1982, 2006; Oke *et al.*, 2017; World Meteorological

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Organization (WMO), 2023). Alternatively, crowdsourcing data and the use of citizen weather stations or crowd weather stations (CWS) have proven to be a valuable source for urban climate studies to overcome the low spatial density of professional weather station networks (Chapman *et al.*, 2017; Muller *et al.*, 2015). Novel data sources such as CWS have also become an integral part of the emerging research field of urban climate informatics (Middel *et al.*, 2022).

Cities are typically warmer than their rural surroundings, an effect referred to as the urban heat island (UHI). The spatio-temporal patterns of the UHI are influenced by many different factors, most importantly land use, built-up structure, building materials, and anthropogenic heat emissions, as well as the portion of impervious surfaces, all influencing the surface energy balance (Oke, 1982; Oke *et al.*, 2017). This leads to differences in air temperature, land surface temperature, and sub-surface temperature between the city and its rural surroundings (Behre, 1908; Fenner *et al.*, 2017; Howard, 1833; Oke *et al.*, 2017; Pepler, 1929; Perlewitz, 1890; Potgieter *et al.*, 2021; Schmidt, 1929; Varentsov *et al.*, 2021). Spatial patterns of the air temperature and canopy layer UHI are most commonly studied under ideal cloud-free and calm conditions, which are often selected specifically for urban climate simulations. Effects such as urban heat advection (UHA), where air that has been warmed up within the densely built-up city (core) is transported leeward to other areas within the city or outside (Lowry, 1977), are often neglected. The process of UHA follows the wind direction, whereas, in contrast, processes such as country breezes (Oke *et al.*, 2017) are omnidirectional. In contrast to UHA, during country breezes cool air is transported from rural surroundings towards the city (core) following a pressure gradient between surrounding rural areas and the city core, a phenomenon called urban heat island circulation (Haeger-Eugensson & Holmer, 1999; Hidalgo *et al.*, 2008a, 2008b, 2010; Oke *et al.*, 2017). UHA has often been considered a process in the urban boundary layer leading to the development of an urban plume leeward of the city (Fenner *et al.*, 2024; Oke *et al.*, 2017; Varentsov *et al.*, 2018). Ignoring the effect of UHA in the urban canopy layer can cause an underestimation of the actual exposure of areas to urban heat and ultimately to inaccurate identification of vulnerable populations (Heaviside *et al.*, 2015) and incorrect decisions in urban adaptation planning and risk management (Bassett *et al.*, 2016).

Brandsma *et al.* (2003) previously investigated the effect of UHA on long-term time series of professional weather stations located in the rural surroundings of a city (De Bilt, the Netherlands), stating that the effect of UHA can reach up to 1 K and has an influence of +0.1 K on the

annual mean temperature of rural professional weather stations. Bohnenstengel *et al.* (2011) describe the effects of UHA using model runs for the UHI of London (UK). Heaviside *et al.* (2015) performed mesoscale simulations of heatwave conditions for the Birmingham (UK) area, using the Weather Research and Forecasting Model (WRF), and concluded that areas located downwind of cities may be up to 2.5 K warmer than areas located upwind. Bassett *et al.* (2016) used a dense station network of 29 stations in Birmingham (Warren *et al.*, 2016), describing a warming effect of up to 1.2 K for downwind areas, which reached over 10 km into the rural surroundings. Further, Bassett *et al.* (2017) scaled the approach to the entire UK and varying city sizes. They investigated the effect of UHA on UK Met Office stations and concluded that stations, even though located in rural areas outside a city, may not be representative of the regional climate due to the effect of the nearby city, with differences between urban and rural upwind sectors of up to 0.6 K (Bassett *et al.*, 2017). Shih *et al.* (2024) investigated the effect for the Taipei Basin (Taiwan) using a meteorological network of 28 stations and reported nighttime effects of 1.75 K. These studies state that the main limitation for further UHA analysis is the density of measurement stations (Bassett *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Heaviside *et al.*, 2015).

Investigations of urban thermal climate conditions and the UHI effect have increasingly been carried out using crowdsourced CWS data, while simultaneously investigating their suitability for such studies (Meier *et al.*, 2017; Napoly *et al.*, 2018; Wolters & Brandsma, 2012). Studies focused on the differentiation of mesoscale and local-scale drivers of the UHI (Potgieter *et al.*, 2021; Varentsov *et al.*, 2021) or its intra-urban variability (Fenner *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, CWS data have provided a valuable training data source for modeling intra-urban temperature distributions based on urban descriptive predictors (Venter *et al.*, 2020; Vulova *et al.*, 2020; Zumwald *et al.*, 2021). CWS also proved valuable for improving local weather prediction models (Blunn *et al.*, 2024; Nipen *et al.*, 2020) and have been used for microscale model evaluations (van der Linden *et al.*, 2023) and comparisons with satellite-derived land surface temperature (Krelaus *et al.*, 2023, 2024; Naserikia *et al.*, 2023, 2024; Venter *et al.*, 2021). Longer, multi-annual periods have been studied by Brousse *et al.* (2022), covering six years of CWS data from the greater London area, and by Fenner *et al.* (2019) using five years of CWS data in Berlin (Germany). Less commonly, data for other variables such as wind speed and direction (Droste *et al.*, 2020), atmospheric pressure (Demortier *et al.*, 2024; Madaus *et al.*, 2014; Mandement & Caumont, 2020), and precipitation (Bárdossy *et al.*, 2021; de Vos *et al.*, 2019) have been utilized from CWS.

The initial data quality of crowdsourced data is generally low, due to inaccurate metadata or the station being setup incorrectly, for example, close to a building (wall) or exposed to direct radiation (Meier *et al.*, 2017; Muller *et al.*, 2015). To overcome data quality issues, many studies focused on implementing quality control (QC) procedures by either using data from professional weather stations (Beele *et al.*, 2022; Meier *et al.*, 2017) or relying solely on CWS data (Båserud *et al.*, 2020; Fenner *et al.*, 2021; Grassmann *et al.*, 2018; Napoly *et al.*, 2018; Nipen *et al.*, 2020), utilizing the “wisdom of the crowd” (Fenner *et al.*, 2021). Given that, after QC, CWS can provide measurements with high spatio-temporal resolution, such data are suitable for studying meso- and microscale urban effects such as UHA. To overcome the previously mentioned limitation of station density, Brousse *et al.* (2022), for the first time, used six years of data from 1560 CWS for the city of London, allowing them also to unveil the intra-urban effects of UHA. Results show an average contribution of 0.22 ± 0.96 K, and up to 1.57 K at maximum, to the UHI intensity.

Summarizing from these studies, the UHA effect can be hypothesized as wind causing urban heat to be transported downwind, leading to increased exposure to urban heat for downwind areas and less exposure for areas located upwind, modifying the spatial pattern of the UHI (Figure 1). Elaborating further on the hypothesis, most urban heat is generated in densely built-up areas in the city core, such as local climate zone (LCZ) 1 (compact highrise). Less heat is generated in more open urban areas such as LCZ 6 (open lowrise). Wind transports the heat

produced leeward across other areas, hence those areas are exposed to additional urban heat compared with calm conditions. With the air masses reaching rural areas, the overall contribution of UHA to increased air temperature is strongest compared with calm conditions, when, typically, little urban heat reaches rural areas. With increasing distance from the city, the effect decreases, up to a critical distance where the effect is no longer present, which may depend on city size, urban form and function, UHI intensity, and wind speed, among other factors. In contrast, on the windward side of the city, areas also receive (relative) cooling, since the locally produced heat is transported leeward and replaced by cool air from the rural surroundings. Factors such as the UHI intensity and wind speed may have effects on the amplitudes ($A_{cooling}$ and $A_{warming}$). Wind speeds may influence the phase lengths further ($P_{cooling}$ and $P_{warming}$). The pattern of UHA will be overlaid by local influences such as small-scale differences in land use and built-up structures such as large impervious surfaces or inner-urban green spaces. The UHA effect might not be present under certain conditions such as strong mesoscale forcings or conditions without any wind.

In this study, quality-controlled data from a dense network of CWS and ERA5–Land reanalysis data (Muñoz-Sabater *et al.*, 2021) are combined with the LCZ scheme (Stewart & Oke, 2012) to overcome the spatial gaps present in professional weather station networks (Bassett *et al.*, 2016, 2017), also enabling the exploration of intra-urban spatial patterns, which previously have only been available from modeling studies (Heaviside *et al.*, 2015). Using data for a period of five years

FIGURE 1 The hypothesis of urban heat advection (UHA) for an idealized concentric and symmetric city. Light winds are approaching the city from the left-hand side across different built-up structures indicated as Local Climate Zones (LCZ), with LCZ 1 (compact highrise), LCZ 2 (compact midrise), LCZ 5 (open midrise), LCZ 6 (open lowrise), LCZ 9 (sparsely built), LCZ A (dense trees), and LCZ D (low plants) providing cooling to areas on the upwind side of the city. Areas downwind of the city core experience exposure to additional urban heat. A = amplitude, P = phase length. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/terms-and-conditions)]

further allows us to quantify the effect of UHA across spatio-temporal scales, including different wind speeds from different wind directions (Brousse *et al.*, 2022), ultimately covering most of the typical climatological conditions of cities.

2 | DATA AND METHODS

2.1 | Study areas and period

This study focuses on the larger metropolitan regions of Paris (France) and Berlin (Germany) (Figure S1.1 in the Supporting Information). The regions were selected due to their exceptionally high number of available CWS. In Paris, a total of 16,754 individual stations, and in Berlin a total of 5,390 stations, were available after QC (Section 2.2) for the study period of five years between January 1, 2019, 0000 UTC and January 1, 2024, 0000 UTC. In addition, both cities are inland cities in relatively flat topography, so effects such as sea breezes (Potgieter *et al.*, 2021) or orography-induced winds are not the source of prevailing winds, as shown by the wind roses (Figure S2.1). Both cities are located within the Köppen Geiger zone Cfb (Kottek *et al.*, 2006). For both cities, the main wind directions are either west (Figure S2.1b) or southwest (Figure S2.1a), with winds carrying moist Atlantic air or easterly winds with drier, continental air masses (Gerstengarbe & Werner, 2005).

2.2 | Crowdsourced Netatmo crowd weather station data

Data from Netatmo¹ CWS were used, utilizing the large number of available identical sensors (Chapman *et al.*, 2017). The accuracy of the Netatmo outdoor sensor has been evaluated multiple times, indicating that the manufacturer-provided accuracy of 0.3 K is correct and stable over time (Coney *et al.*, 2022; Mandement & Caumont, 2020; Meier *et al.*, 2017; Varentsov *et al.*, 2020). In addition to the general sensor accuracy, the time lag ($\tau_{63\%}$) was also investigated, indicating slow response times of the sensor ranging between $\tau_{63\%} = 12.7$ minutes (Coney *et al.*, 2022) and $\tau_{63\%} = 22.46$ minutes (Büchau, 2018). These characteristics form a physical baseline for the sensors; however, they will differ based on the setup of the sensors in the field, which may introduce additional errors, making a QC of all data necessary to filter out potentially erroneous measurements.

The Netatmo CWS air-temperature data were extracted from a large database (Fenner *et al.*, 2021) containing hourly mean values of CWS data from over 500 cities

worldwide, starting in 2019. The data were collected continuously, while constantly ensuring metadata quality by

1. adding newly set up stations to the database;
2. updating the metadata of existing stations and classifying them as either “moved” or “updated” and discontinuing or restarting time series of affected stations;
3. only downloading data for time spans during which metadata were observed continuously, considering both the station’s original discovery date and its last active date at the same position. Data are not downloaded before or after these time frames to ensure accurate positioning.

The air-temperature data in the entire database has been quality controlled using the CrowdQC+² R package (Fenner *et al.*, 2021) with default settings. For this study, the quality level $o2(> 80\%$ daily data availability) was selected and the data were filtered accordingly. In addition to the QC provided by CrowdQC+, an annual data availability of at least 80% per station and year in at least one of the five years of the study period was required for a station to be included in the analyses. If a station did not fulfill the criterion, it was removed for the entire year, harmonizing long-term data and avoiding imbalances of data availability across months.

For all calculations and statistical tests, only nocturnal hours—when the difference between urban and rural air temperature (ta) is typically most pronounced—were used (Figure S3.1). This difference is defined as Δta (K) = ta_{CWS} (°C) – ta_{rural} (°C). For Berlin and Paris, the hours between 2000 UTC and 0600 UTC were selected.

2.3 | The spatial effect of wind direction and wind speed

To investigate the effects of wind speed and wind direction on the spatial patterns of the UHI, a multi-step process was developed (Table 1). In step 0a, 10-m wind speed, 10-m wind direction (calculated from u_{10} and v_{10}) and 2-m air temperature (t_{2m}) were extracted from ERA5–Land data (Muñoz-Sabater *et al.*, 2021) with $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (~ 9 km) grid spacing and one-hourly temporal resolution. The Δta per CWS was calculated per hour as $\Delta ta = ta_{CWS} - ta_{rural}$, where ta_{CWS} is the hourly average air temperature at any CWS and ta_{rural} the spatial hourly average t_{2m} of all ERA5–Land pixels within a bounding box around all available CWS in the study area (Figure S1.1: step 0b, Table 1). The ERA5–Land dataset is a suitable dataset in this respect, as it does not include an urban model in its framework (ECMWF, 2018; Muñoz-Sabater *et al.*, 2021). Urban areas are classified as “Crops, Mixed Farming”,

TABLE 1 Summary of the methodological steps to (1) compare the spatial patterns of UHA and (2) test statistical significance for dynamic wind sectors and (3b) wind-speed classes, as well as (3c) per station. The data preparation step (0) was conducted before each step (1)–(3).

Step	Description
0. Data preparation	
(a) Extract “u10”, “v10”, and “t2m” from ERA5–Land	Use all pixels intersecting with CWS, forming the region of interest (ROI) in hourly temporal resolution.
(b) Calculate Δta per CWS per hour	Use $\Delta ta = ta_{CWS} - ta_{rural}$.
(c) Calculate average of ERA5–Land wind speed and wind direction	Use all pixels in the ROI and calculate the spatial average of the “u” and “v” vector components in hourly temporal resolution and convert it to wind direction ($^{\circ}$) and wind speed ($m \cdot s^{-1}$).
(d) Calculate estimation of standard deviation of wind direction	Use Yamartino (1984) to estimate the standard deviation of the wind direction over a moving window of six hours. Only select hours with $\sigma_{\theta} < 10^{\circ}$.
1. Static inter-cardinal approach	
(a) Classify into four inter-cardinal sectors	Each sector spans 90° : ((0, 90]), ((90, 180]), ((180, 270]), ((270, 360]).
(b) Create regular hexagonal grid	Use ROI to generate regular grid of hexagons (1500 m side length). Assign each CWS to a hexagon.
(c) Average Δta values per hexagon and wind sector	Average only if \geq three stations are in hexagon. Generate one map per intercardinal direction.
(d) Scale each map individually using the robust scaler (Pedregosa <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	The scaling removes the median and scales all values to the interquartile range so they can be compared with each other.
(e) Calculate a mean scaled pattern	All four maps are averaged to form a mean scaled spatial pattern.
(f) Subtract mean scaled pattern from each sector-specific scaled pattern	To highlight spatial differences and deviations from the mean scaled pattern, each sector-specific scaled pattern is subtracted from the mean scaled pattern, returning four maps of spatial pattern differences.
2. Dynamic approach	
(a) Determine city core point	Weights are assigned to each LCZ class and a weighted K-means clustering (Lloyd, 1982; Pedregosa <i>et al.</i> , 2011) is applied yielding a city core.
(b) Define dynamic 90° sectors based on ERA5–Land wind direction	For each hour, create dynamic wind sectors around the city core by adding 45° to the wind direction and subtracting 45° from the wind direction, forming an “upwind” sector. Its inverse is classified as “downwind”, the remaining two sectors as “lateral”.
(c) Use Wilcoxon signed-rank (Wilcoxon, 1945) test to compare groups	Compare previously classified up- and downwind groups against each other and test that downwind sector $>$ upwind sector.
3. Critical wind speeds	
(a) Create $1 m \cdot s^{-1}$ wind-speed categories	ERA5-derived wind speeds (step 0c) are rounded to the nearest integer value
(b) Wilcoxon signed-rank test per wind-speed class	Perform a Wilcoxon signed-rank test per wind-speed class and compare up- and downwind sectors.
(c) Additional Wilcoxon signed-rank test per station	Perform a Wilcoxon signed-rank test per wind-speed class and per station comparing up- and downwind situations.

based on the Global Land-Cover Characteristics (GLSS: Loveland *et al.*, 2000) and the Biosphere–Atmosphere Transfer Scheme (BATS). That way ERA5–Land captures the regional rural background air-temperature conditions in an appropriate manner for our purpose without specifically considering the urban effect (Jacobs *et al.*, 2024; Nogueira *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, it has global coverage and thus provides rural background air temperature for

any city. This is particularly relevant, as CWS coverage is typically low in natural environments (Brousse *et al.*, 2022; Fenner *et al.*, 2017; Potgieter *et al.*, 2021), making UHI calculations based solely on CWS difficult, if not impossible in many instances. The ERA5–Land data were acquired via Google Earth Engine (Gorelick *et al.*, 2017).

To differentiate between situations with frequently shifting winds and situations with winds coming from

a homogeneous direction, an approximation of the standard deviation of the wind direction was calculated using the method by Yamartino (1984) (see Section S5, Equations S5.1–S5.4). The calculation was applied to all data using a right-aligned moving average of six hours. Considering shifts in wind direction, only values of Δta , where its corresponding σ_θ was $< 10^\circ$ (approximated standard deviation of the hourly wind directions), were selected. For all further calculations performed, the wind direction is homogeneous to this degree (step 0d, Table 1).

Based on the spatial average (vector means) of ERA5–Land wind direction (step 0c, Table 1) in the region of interest (ROI: Figure S1.1), all hourly values of Δta were, for later comparison, divided into the four ordinal wind directions/intercardinal directions spanning 90° each (step 1a, Table 1): from north to east ((0, 90]), from east to south ((90, 180]), from south to west ((180, 270]), and from west to north ((270, 360]) (see Figure S1.1).

For the investigations of spatial UHI patterns, a regular hexagonal grid was created for each city (length of one side of a hexagon 1500 m; step 1b, Table 1). The Δta values of all intersecting CWS were then averaged per respective hexagon, resulting in one value of Δta per hexagon and wind sector. Only hexagons containing at least three stations were included in the final analysis for robust results, reducing the influence of individual CWS (cf. Napoly *et al.*, 2018; Chapman *et al.*, 2023; step 1c, Table 1). Due to the highly dynamic nature of CWS, individual hexagons may contain a varying subset of stations over the study period, constrained by the spatial extent of the hexagon and data availability restriction applied on an annual basis (Section 2.2). This variability arises from missing data—due to either stations not recording or removal during QC—as well as from stations being uninstalled.

To compare the spatial patterns between wind directions, each map of hexagons of averaged values of Δta (one map per wind direction) was scaled individually using the robust scaler (Equation 1). The median is removed and the data are scaled to the interquartile range (Pedregosa *et al.*, 2011). The method was chosen over a min/max (scaling lowest value to 0, highest to 1) or standard scaler (removing the mean and scaling to unit variance) so that potential outliers have lower effects (step 1d, Table 1):

$$X_{\text{scaled}} = \frac{X_i - \tilde{X}}{IQR}, \quad (1)$$

where X_i is the value to be scaled, \tilde{X} the median, and finally X_{scaled} the scaled value.

A mean spatial pattern was calculated by averaging over all four wind-sector-specific scaled patterns (step 1e,

TABLE 2 Weights used to calculate the city core based on a centroid of a K-means algorithm (Lloyd, 1982; Pedregosa *et al.*, 2011) per LCZ. The weights are based on the urban characteristics (geometric and surface-cover properties) of the LCZs (Stewart & Oke, 2012).

LCZ Class	Weight	Note
1	10^5	
2	10^4	
3	10^2	Limited presence in Paris and Berlin
4	10^2	Limited presence in Paris and Berlin
5	10^4	
6	10^1	
7	10^0	Not present in Paris and Berlin
8	10^2	

Table 1; Figures S4.1 and S11.1), to then be subtracted from each sector-specific scaled pattern, resulting in the deviation of each wind-sector-specific pattern from the mean pattern, respectively (Figure S11.1). This way, spatial differences caused by different wind directions can be made visible (step 1f, Table 1).

To compare the upwind and downwind parts of the city, a dynamic approach was taken to classify upwind and downwind sectors. A city core point was calculated based on a K-means cluster analysis and LCZs, using a centroid of a single cluster, weighting the points (LCZ pixels) by their corresponding LCZ class (Table 2). Lloyd's algorithm (Lloyd, 1982), with added sample weights, was used. The weights are based on the urban characteristics (geometric and surface-cover properties) of the LCZs as described by Stewart and Oke (2012). Only urban LCZs, except LCZ 9 (sparsely built) and LCZ 10 (heavy industry), were considered (step 2a, Table 1). The resulting city cores for Paris and Berlin are 48.8436°N ; 2.3384°E and 52.5049°N ; 13.4081°E , respectively.

Based on the hypothesis that a large fraction of the urban heat is present around the city core and with winds transporting it downwind, sectors are expected to widen with increasing distance from the city core. To account for shifting winds, or wind directions not matching the four static intercardinal sectors, a dynamic approach was chosen, always placing the prevailing wind direction in the center of each sector. To calculate these wind-direction-dependent moving sectors of 90° angle around the city core, 45° were added (subtracted) to the spatially averaged hourly ERA5–Land wind direction to form the upper (lower) boundary. This sector forms the upwind sector and its inverse the downwind sector. Stations intersecting with either sector were classified as

up- or downwind, accordingly. No class was assigned to all other stations with lateral winds (Figure S6.1). The classification was applied to every hour in the dataset for the entire study period (step 2b, Table 1). This method also addresses potential biases introduced by a systematic shift of the spatial peak of Δta along the axis of the prevailing wind direction, making up- and downwind comparisons more robust.

The non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test (Wilcoxon, 1945) was then used to compare up- and downwind groups, since a normal distribution cannot be guaranteed. A one-sided alternative hypothesis H_1 was selected, stating that the downwind group distribution shows higher values than its upwind pair. Per-station differences between up- and downwind conditions were calculated. A significance level of 1% was chosen for all statistical tests (step 2c, Table 1).

2.4 | Calculating critical wind speeds

To examine the impact of wind speed on the UHA, wind-speed categories were established by rounding the hourly wind-speed values to the nearest integer (step 3a, Table 1). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test was then conducted for each wind-speed class, comparing the down- and upwind classes as groups (step 3b, Table 1). In addition, the difference between down- and upwind conditions was calculated on a per-station, per-wind-speed-category, and per-hour basis (step 3c, Table 1, Figure S11.2). The results were used to identify the wind speeds with the greatest differences between up- and downwind sectors (critical wind speeds). To investigate the spatial pattern of the test significances, Wilcoxon tests per station and per wind-speed category were conducted, yielding test statistics and a p -value per station and per wind-speed category (step 3c, Table 1). Critical wind speeds refer to a threshold at which vertical turbulent mixing between the urban canopy layer and the overlying atmospheric boundary layer becomes more dominant than horizontal wind-driven transport of air within the urban canopy layer, ultimately reducing the effect of UHA.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Spatial patterns of urban heat advection

The subtraction of the average scaled UHI pattern (all wind directions) from the wind-direction-specific scaled pattern (step 1f, Table 1; Figures 2b and 3b) yields spatial air-temperature differences caused by advection.

Compared with the mean scaled pattern, areas downwind of the city core show higher values of Δta than upwind and lateral sectors. This holds true for all four wind-direction sectors analyzed. The scaling of the values of Δta allows us to compare only the differences in spatial patterns, regardless of the absolute magnitude of Δta . A Wilcoxon test including all stations yields statistically significant differences between downwind and upwind conditions (step 2d, Table 1). With certain wind directions, the area around the city core shows lower values of Δta compared with average conditions (northeasterly, northwesterly), while for southwesterly winds the city core displays higher values of Δta than average conditions (Figures 2c and 3c). Results are similar for both cities.

In Figure 4, absolute differences between downwind and upwind conditions are displayed. It is visible that most stations show positive values of up to 3.6 K, but stations in the northeast show no differences or even negative values, especially for Paris with negative values up to -2.7 K (Figure 4a). For Berlin (Figure 4b), this is less pronounced (-1.4 K), but areas northeast of the city core also show slightly negative values. Other areas in the northeast show values close to 0 K. The differences are likely the result of different weather conditions, resulting in varying strengths of the UHI, with southwesterly conditions often associated with lower levels of Δta and northeasterly ones with higher levels of Δta , canceling each other out (see Section 4.1 for more details).

3.2 | Wind speeds and urban heat advection

On average, the difference in Δta between upwind and downwind conditions is 0.71 K for Paris and 0.33 K for Berlin (Figure S6.2). Taking different wind speeds into account, the differences between downwind and upwind sectors are generally highest for wind speeds of $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure 5).

The Wilcoxon test statistics per wind-speed class show that differences between down- and upwind sectors are significant for wind speeds higher than or equal to $1 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, up until $6 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Above this, statistical tests are not significant for Berlin (Figure 5).

For Paris and Berlin, data availability for situations with wind speeds of 0 or $\geq 7 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ is low (Tables S6.1 and S6.2), hence the confidence interval is larger and p -values are higher than for the other wind-speed classes, or close to the 1% significance level.

In Figure 6, the UHI intensity (Δta) is shown for each wind-speed class for both stations, downwind and upwind. The upwind areas generally show lower values of Δta . The strongest differences between up- and downwind also

(b) Scaled UHI using robust scaler

(c) Differences between scaled UHI (b) and mean conditions (average of all four)

FIGURE 2 (a) Mean absolute nocturnal UHI patterns, (b) mean scaled UHI patterns using a robust scaler (Section 2.3), and (c) differences between scaled patterns and mean scaled conditions of the UHI per wind direction for the greater Paris region during 2019–2023, 2000–0600 UTC. The black cross marks the city core. Projection: EPSG:3035 ETRS89-extended/LAEA Europe, background map: Demuzere *et al.* (2022). [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.5065)]

appear with the strongest UHI intensity (e.g., at wind speeds of $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). Wind speeds of $0 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ show the largest interquartile range and overall range but also have

a low n , since completely calm conditions are rare. For Paris (Figure 6a), decreasing values of Δt_a with increasing wind speeds are visible. Differences between up- and

FIGURE 3 Same as Figure 2, but for Berlin. (a) Absolute values in K, not scaled, (b) scaled values using a robust scaler, (c) differences between scaled spatial patterns as shown in (b). [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

downwind sectors are also visible for higher wind speeds. For Berlin (Figure 6b), the overall pattern is similar with, however, a lower magnitude of Δta . It is found that, even for higher wind speeds of up to $6 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, differences are still statistically significant. Limited data availability did not allow for a robust analysis of higher wind speeds. For

Berlin, results $\geq 7 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ are not statistically significant (Figure 5).

For wind speeds of $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, the median difference between up- and downwind conditions is 0.72 K (mean 0.63 K) for Paris (Figure 5 and Table S6.1) and 0.45 K (mean 0.46 K) for Berlin (Figure 5 and Table S6.2). The

FIGURE 4 Average differences between nocturnal downwind and upwind conditions ($\Delta t_{\text{downwind}} - \Delta t_{\text{upwind}}$) per station for all wind directions (using dynamic downwind and upwind sectors (see Section 2.3) for (a) Paris and (b) Berlin during 2019–2023, 2000–0600 UTC. The black cross marks the city core. Note the different color bar scales. Projection: EPSG:3035 ETRS89-extended/LAEA Europe, background map: Demuzere *et al.* (2022). [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 5 Differences in nocturnal air temperature between downwind and upwind sectors per wind-speed class in Paris (left) and Berlin (right). The significances of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test performed are displayed as dots (significant to 1%) and crosses (not significant). The corresponding p -values are shown as shading from light (closer to 1) to dark (closer to zero). The number of samples (n) varies between classes and is shown at the bottom for each class. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

effect can also reach up to 1.86 K (Q_{95}) for Paris and 1.51 K (Q_{95}) for Berlin. Individual stations can reach up to 3.46 K (Paris) and 2.83 K (Berlin). However, differences between downwind and upwind regions are not always positive. Individual stations also indicate slightly negative values (Tables S6.1 and S6.2). For additional information, see also Section S6 in the Supporting Information.

While average UHA patterns (Figures 2c and 3c) have a lower intensity than the UHI intensity (Figures 2a and 3a),

the UHA effect can be substantially stronger during certain conditions. An example for each of the two cities is given in Figure 7. For Paris (Figure 7a), winds are between 2.3 and 2.8 $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and consistently from the east. Over the six hours analyzed, the UHA pattern changes and the effect intensifies towards the morning (Figure S10.2). For the Berlin example (Figure 7b), wind speeds are between 2.4 and 2.6 $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ from the northeast. Over the time period, the pattern weakens towards the morning.

FIGURE 6 Nocturnal Δt_a for each wind-speed class for stations downwind (blue) and upwind (brown) of the city core for (a) Paris and (b) Berlin during 2019–2023, 2000–0600 UTC. Boxes display the interquartile range with median (horizontal line), whiskers are ≤ 1.5 times the interquartile range, values above or below that are marked as diamonds. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.5065)]

FIGURE 7 Nocturnal UHI patterns for an example night-time period with strong UHA for (a) Paris (September 1, 2022, 2200–0300 UTC) and (b) Berlin (April 18, 2022, 1900–0000 UTC). Station observations were aggregated to hexagons with a side length of 500 m and averaged over six hours. The prevailing (angle-average) wind direction derived from ERA5–Land is indicated as an arrow and mean wind speed and direction values are given. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/terms-and-conditions)]

The strongest advection of urban heat is visible between 1900 and 2000 UTC (Figure S10.3). During both cases, wind speeds are at the optimum value for UHA (or just below) of $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (see Section 3.2, Tables S6.1 and S6.2, Figures 5 and 6). For additional examples, see Section S10 and Figure S10.1 in the Supplementary Material. Further analyses on atmospheric boundary-layer dynamics during this case-study day in Berlin can be found in Fenner *et al.* (2024).

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | Relative spatial differences between wind directions

Utilizing the large number of available CWS, we are able to show intra-urban spatial patterns and regional distributions of UHA with observational data. The effect of the prevailing wind direction on the leeward transport

FIGURE 8 Exemplary transect analysis of scaled Δta for selected cases in (a) Paris (September 2, 2022, 0300 UTC) and (b) Berlin (April 18, 2022, 2100 UTC). Transect width is 2000 m, intersecting the city core and following the prevailing wind direction (ERA5–Land), indicated with an arrow. Left panels show a side view of the transects from upwind (negative values on x-axis) to downwind regions, with average scaled (2019–2023, blue) and case-date scaled Δta (orange) for individual CWS (dots) and a fitted sixth-degree polynomial (lines) with maxima indicated by vertical dashed lines, with horizontal distance between the two maxima given as a number. The difference between case-date and average scaled Δta per CWS is shown as a green line (1-km binned average) and shading (95% CI) (cf. Supporting Information Section S9 for further details on the methods and calculations and Figure S9.1 for an unscaled version). Projection: EPSG:3035 ETRS89-extended/LAEA Europe (Figure 8b). [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.5065)]

of urban heat is demonstrated and significant effects are shown (Section 3.2). In a novel approach, a robust scaler was chosen to be able to compare spatial patterns of different magnitudes. A gradient of UHA as hypothesized (Figure 1) from the city core towards the rural areas is visible, being close to zero around the city core (Figure 2c). However, the decrease of the UHA with increasing distance from the city core is not clearly visible. A more detailed analysis could be carried out to analyze and quantify this effect further. To exemplarily investigate and illustrate the advection effect in relation to the distance to the city core, the example cases per city (Figure 7) with strong UHA were selected and compared with the average UHI pattern (cf. Supplementary Material Section S9 for further details on the methods and calculations). A spatial shift of the peak of Δta downwind is observed in both cases (Figure 8a,b as well as Figure S9.1 (unscaled)). As indicated by the difference between the average situation and the current situation, a decreasing cooling effect towards

the city core is visible, along with an initially increasing warming effect that eventually decreases. A larger domain size would be needed to investigate the decreasing effect further. These initial results indicate that the distance of the maximum peak is dependent on the wind speed: for lower wind speeds than $2.5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure S9.4), the peak is shifted less downwind than for higher wind speeds of, for example, $2.5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure S9.3). The correlation of a spatial shift in peak Δta and wind speed, however, needs further, more in-depth investigation.

As indicated by the difference between the average situation and the current situation, a decreasing cooling effect towards the city core is visible, along with an initially increasing warming effect that eventually decreases.

Due to the nature of CWS, measurements are primarily available inside the city and also are likely distributed spatially unequally with lower coverage in deprived areas, following socio-economic inequalities (Brousse *et al.*, 2024). The aggregation on a hexagon level with at least three

available stations likely reduced the rural data availability further. It was shown by Bassett *et al.* (2016, 2017) that the effects of UHA reach far into the rural surroundings. Larger rural areas need to be covered to investigate the full scale of the effect.

The approach developed performs well for a detailed and quantified comparison of spatial patterns. This approach, however, does not allow for quantification of the absolute (in K) or relative (in %) magnitude of the effect. Different approaches, on a per-station basis, were taken to quantify the effect instead. In the cases of northeasterly and southwesterly winds, large differences appear around the city core. This may be due to a shift of the peak of the UHI along the axis of the wind direction, combined with weather patterns being different with southwesterly and northeasterly winds (see Section 4.3). It was found that the average UHI intensity differs depending on the wind direction (Figure 2a). The strongest UHI develops with northeasterly winds and dry continental air masses, the weakest with southwesterly winds transporting moist maritime air masses (see Section 2.1, Figures 2a and 3a) for Paris and Berlin, respectively. This could explain the differences in the city core for these two opposite cases, since for southeasterly and northwesterly winds such a pattern is not visible. Both of these wind directions show only marginal differences in the average UHI intensity patterns. For the dynamic wind-sector approach (Section 2.3), triangular-shaped (circle segments) up- and downwind sectors were created (Figure S6.1) and these enabled the analysis of long time spans with shifting wind directions. The results of the spatial patterns indicate that the approach will likely not include all up- and downwind stations fully and stations will be incorrectly classified as lateral (neither upwind nor downwind), hence the number of up- and downwind stations was potentially underestimated, especially towards the city core.

4.2 | Influence of the wind speed on urban heat advection

The metric used in this study describes the difference between the downwind conditions and upwind conditions ($\Delta ta_{\text{downwind}} - \Delta ta_{\text{upwind}}$), and thus includes both the cooling provided to upwind regions and the heat advected to downwind regions (Figure 1). Initially excluding the influence of wind speed, our results reveal an average temperature difference between downwind and upwind conditions of 0.33 K for Berlin and 0.71 K for Paris (Section 3.1 and Figure S6.2). For both Paris (Figure S6.2a) and Berlin (Figure S6.2b), the upwind conditions show lower values than the downwind conditions, and both

groups differ significantly at a 1% significance level, proving the presence and influence of UHA.

When comparing the results with other studies, the difference in methodology needs to be considered. Brandsma *et al.* (2003) described the effect of UHA as 0.1 K on average. Due to only using a single station, the influence was limited to certain wind sectors only, where the station was located downwind. Also, the difference in city size between Utrecht, NL, De Bilt, NL, Paris, and Berlin has to be taken into account when comparing values. Brousse *et al.* (2022) describe the effect of UHA for London as 0.22 ± 0.96 K, reaching up to 1.57 K. For Birmingham, Bassett *et al.* (2016) report values up to 1.2 K. Shih *et al.* (2024) report values of up to 1.75 K for the Taipei Basin (Taiwan). For smaller urban areas, Bassett *et al.* (2017) report values up to 0.6 K. In this study, under certain conditions, the effect reached up to 1.95 K (Q_{95}). It was found (Section 3.2) that the strongest UHA appears at $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. With a weaker UHA effect at lower ($0\text{--}1 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) and higher wind speeds ($> 6 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), the resulting curves are bell-shaped (Figure 5). Assuming that the UHI intensity is constant, for low wind speeds not enough airflow is available to transport the urban heat from the city core towards rural areas. With increasing wind speeds, more urban heat can be transported leeward and hence large areas are affected by advected urban heat. Exceeding a critical wind speed (found to be $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), the effect decreases again due to (turbulent) mixing in the atmospheric boundary layer, until the effect is not present any longer.

The results are consistent with what has been reported for other cities: for example, a maximum at $2.2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for Utrecht and $3.9 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for wind coming via De Bilt (Brandsma *et al.*, 2003), between 2 and $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for Birmingham (Bassett *et al.*, 2016), and in the $3\text{--}6 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ category following the Beaufort scale for London (Brousse *et al.*, 2022) and the Taipei Basin (Taiwan) (Shih *et al.*, 2024). It can be concluded that the strongest UHA appears around wind speeds of $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ across different cities.

The metric developed currently does not differentiate between advection-induced cooling and advection-induced heating and provides a combined difference. Further investigations could focus on utilizing the lateral wind sectors as a potential reference. However, attention needs to be paid to the role of the city core, currently defined as a point. Results indicate that the analysis is, to some degree, sensitive to its definition. The effect of using a circular area as city core instead could be explored in future analyses. The city core defined in this study was compared with the city core calculated in the context of the *urbisphere* project (Fenner *et al.*, 2024), where different datasets such as building fraction, vegetated fraction, building volume, population density, and

anthropogenic heat flux (table A1 therein) were used to determine a city core. All parameters used are also represented in the LCZ system, however on a larger scale of up to several hundreds of meters. The distance between the city core points was found to be 1790 m for Berlin and 1929 m for Paris (Figure S1.1). This showcases that our simple approach based on LCZ classes on a 100-m grid resolution provides results comparable with a more sophisticated approach that relies on high-resolution datasets (Fenner *et al.*, 2024) not available globally. A limiting factor that was not explored in our analyses is the city shape. The proposed method will likely only be applicable to cities with a relatively concentric structure, such as Paris and Berlin. In addition to this, further studies could investigate the seasonality, focusing on the changing UHI intensity: for example, due to varying anthropogenic heat flux across seasons, caused by heating during winter and cooling during summer. Furthermore, since this study does not differentiate the UHA effect by season, future research could explore the seasonal variability of UHA, with a focus on changes in UHI intensity throughout the year. With the constantly growing availability of CWS data, this may become feasible in the future.

4.3 | Spatial distribution of urban heat advection

The spatial distribution of the Wilcoxon-test significances (Figures S8.1 and S8.2) as well as the spatial distribution of the downwind and upwind differences (Figure 4) can be explained with typical weather patterns. With strong UHI and sufficient wind speeds ($2\text{--}3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, Figure 5), strong advection also develops, which is the case with north-easterly winds. Southwesterly winds show the opposite effect, with only weak UHI development. Because of this, the northeasterly sector experiences less heat advection when downwind (southwesterly winds), but when located upwind (northeasterly winds) the UHI is simultaneously strong. As a result, downwind–upwind differences cancel each other out and the difference becomes marginal, resulting in the Wilcoxon test being unable to detect significant differences between downwind and upwind situations for those areas. The opposite is the case for the southwest sector. On the one hand, while the situation is downwind (northeasterly winds) the UHI is typically strong, hence strong advection also takes place. On the other hand, with southwesterly winds the UHI is weak, so differences between up- and downwind situations are increased. This also explains the spatial differences in average advected heat, with the northeast areas showing no or even negative differences and the southwest areas showing high differences (Figure 4).

This could be addressed by performing a weather-type classification based on synoptic conditions characterizing a city (Hidalgo & Jouglu, 2018), exploring further the link between synoptic conditions and prevailing wind directions (Lamb, 1972). Initial results (Section S7), based on the weather types defined by Bissolli and Dittmann (2001), indicate that for Berlin the strongest differences appear during weather types with northerly wind directions or no prevailing wind directions and anticyclonic conditions at the 950-hPa level (Figure S7.3). Future investigations could focus on unraveling the characteristics of each weather type in combinations of urban heat and specifically UHA. This way, not only prevailing wind directions taken into account but also other factors such as the structure and characteristics of the atmospheric boundary layer. In a further step, the (de-)coupling of the atmospheric boundary layer with the urban canopy layer could be investigated in conjunction with UHA to enhance further our understanding of the processes that govern (intra-)urban heat patterns and UHA in cities (e.g., Céspedes *et al.*, 2024; Haeffelin *et al.*, 2024), making use of detailed data sets of the atmospheric boundary layer (e.g., Fenner *et al.*, 2024; Morrison *et al.*, 2025).

This study focuses on the mesoscale effects of wind speed and wind direction and does not resolve small-scale structures such as individual buildings. While, within the city, wind may, at certain times and places, follow directions that are somewhat inverse to the mesoscale prevailing wind conditions, the overall transport of air across the city will still ultimately follow the dominant wind direction, hence using ERA5–Land with wide sectors of 45° is sufficient to observe the effect of UHA. For local-scale studies, the small-scale heterogeneity of wind speeds (Droste *et al.*, 2018) could be taken into account and further investigation could be made of the effects on local scales: for example, inner-city parks and neighboring built-up areas (Quanz *et al.*, 2018). More complex settings such as coastal areas with sea breezes or mountainous areas could be included in further studies, investigating the interactions with the UHA effect.

The results differ between Paris and Berlin, with Paris, on average, showing higher differences of Δta between up- and downwind conditions while following a similar spatial pattern. Both cities are located in the same Köppen Geiger zone (Cfb); differences in local background climate—for example, caused by the distance from the coast or different latitudes—are likely present. The cities also differ in overall size and in built-up structure, indicated by a different distribution of LCZs, where the ROI of Paris has a larger share of LCZs 1 (0.3%), 2 (2.1%), and 5 (5.6%) than Berlin (0.1%, 0.9%, and 3.6%, as derived from the global map of LCZ using LCZ4r: Anjos *et al.*, 2025). In addition, local sources of (anthropogenic) heat will have an influence on

individual measurements of air temperature at certain stations. By aggregating spatially into hexagons of 1500 m and requiring at least three stations per hexagon, this has little effect on the overall mesoscale pattern. However, further analysis could take these and additional static factors such as population density into account, while also considering the dynamic factors such as wind speed, wind direction, anthropogenic heat flux, and current UHI intensity.

Further investigation is needed, extending the analysis performed in this study to many different cities, this way covering additional combinations of static factors. This will help to parametrize the individual components influencing the effect of UHA. Machine learning could be used to develop a post-processor for neighborhood-scale models that neglect UHA entirely, such as the Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS: Grimmond *et al.*, 2024) or The Air-temperature Response to Green/blue-infrastructure Evaluation Tool (TARGET: Broadbent *et al.*, 2019). These models are computationally inexpensive and post-processing could improve model results further. The crowd database with its wide range of cities would allow for a decent-sized sample to be used as training, test, and validation data.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

The study investigates the effect of UHA using an unprecedented set of CWS for the cities of Paris and Berlin. To reveal spatial patterns of UHA, we (a) introduce a novel approach to determine the city core systematically using a K-means clustering based weighted mean approach considering the spatial distribution of urban LCZs, (b) introduce a dynamic methodology for determining downwind, upwind, and lateral sectors based on the city core, allowing the utilization of all available CWS data in combination with ERA5-Land data, and (c) analyze the dependence of UHA on wind speed. Smaller UHA effects appear with low wind speeds, a maximum UHA effect is reached at a wind speed of $3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, and effects decrease afterwards. It is shown that average differences between down- and upwind conditions are city-specific, with 0.33 K for Berlin and 0.71 K for Paris.

The results presented in this article highlight the necessity to take the effect of wind speed and wind direction on the spatial advection of urban heat into account. Studying urban heat only under ideal, calm conditions and the strongest development of the UHI can lead to a considerable underestimation of urban heat in urban areas. As this study highlights, UHA in the urban canopy layer is a non-negligible effect and hence any dynamical urban climate model focusing on this scale/layer should consider/resolve UHA. Ultimately, the observed effects in the

urban canopy layer could be coupled with observed urban boundary-layer dynamics to study further the interactions between urban boundary-layer and urban canopy-layer conditions.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The underlying CWS data can be accessed via the Netatmo public /getpublicdata (<https://dev.netatmo.com/apidocumentation/weather#getpublicdata>) and /getmeasure (<https://dev.netatmo.com/apidocumentation/weather#getmeasure>) APIs.

The global map of Local Climate Zones by Demuzere *et al.* (2022) is publicly available for download from Zenodo via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6364593>. In this study, version 2 was used.

ERA5–Land data (Muñoz-Sabater *et al.*, 2021) are available via Google Earth Engine: https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/ECMWF_ERA5_LAND_HOURLY or alternatively CDS: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=overview>.

The underlying code will be made available upon request.

ENDNOTES

¹<https://netatmo.com/smart-weather-station>.

²<https://github.com/dafenner/CrowdQCplus>.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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